

FEATURES OF COGNITIVE AND EMOTIONAL DISORDERS IN CHRONIC CEREBRAL ISCHEMIA

Yo'ldosheva Naima Qudratovna

Assistant of the department of OSTA in Bukhara State Medical Institute
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Annotation. Another morphological substrate of cognitive impairment in hypertension may be diffuse injury of this white matter, cortical atrophy, and cerebral hypoperfusion caused by specific structural changes in small intracerebral arterioles. Cortical (granular) atrophy of the hemispheres develops due to the death of neurons, which explains the functional disorders. Several small focal lesions in the deep parts of the brain, spongiosis of the white matter, impairment of higher mental functions lead to scattering of brain structures, particularly the temporal, parietal, as well as limbic-reticular complex structures of the frontal regions.

Key words: metabolic and clinical disorders, vascular brain lesions

Vascular brain lesions are the most common cause of death in many countries of the world. Stroke ranks second in the structure of total mortality in Russia. More than 400 thousand cases of strokes are registered annually, with a mortality rate of up to 35%. The primary disability rate after a stroke is 3.2 per 10,000 people, and no more than 20% of those who previously worked return to work. People with disabilities due to cerebrovascular diseases account for 9.8% of the total contingent of people with disabilities among the population. Statistical data indicate that the increase in vascular diseases of the brain occurs due to an increase in the prevalence of chronic cerebral ischemia (CHEM). In Uzbekistan, according to data from Majidov N.M. (2014), Gafurov B.G. (2021) and others, the number of patients suffering from chronic forms of CVD is about 650-700 thousand.

The purpose of the study. To establish the characteristics of cognitive and emotional disorders in dyscirculatory encephalopathy.

Materials and methods of research. 100 patients with stage I-III DE were examined, 70 women and 30 men (average age 62.4 ± 14.9), of whom up to 50 years (22.3%), up to 60 years (19.3%), up to 70 years (17.8%), up to 80 years (20.3%), over 80 years (20.5%). The examination was conducted on the basis of the neurological department of the regional multidisciplinary medical center of the city of Bukhara. The diagnosis of DE was established on the basis of the classification of E.V.Schmidt (1985), N.N.Yakhno, I.V.Damulin (1995).

The results of the study. The etiological basis for the development of DE in the examined patients were atherosclerosis (29.1%), arterial hypertension

(22.2%), their combination (37.7%) and arterial hypotension (11%). Stage I of DE is characterized by a discrepancy between subjective and objective assessments of neurological status and cognitive functions. At the same time, the most common complaints in patients were complaints of headache (80%) and meteosensitivity (70%). The second most frequent complaints were dizziness and sleep disorders (52.5%), in third place complaints of memory loss (45%), fatigue, general weakness, heaviness in the head and decreased mood (35%). There were fewer complaints of decreased attention, staggering when walking, irritability (25%). Objective examination of patients in this group revealed mainly diffuse microsymptomatology in the form of attenuation of the pupil response to light and convergence, unstable horizontal nystagmus, asymmetry of deep reflexes without clear lateralization, unstable hand reflex Rossolimo. There were no deficient neurological syndromes in stage I of DE, and asthenic syndrome was detected in most patients (85%). Neuropsychological examination revealed that in the absolute majority of patients (90%), attention and long-term auditory memory were significantly below normal. During the examination of praxis and gnosis, no violations were detected, the overall score was within the normal range (24.62 ± 0.79). In some patients, there was a slowdown in performing tests for constructive praxis, without errors. The average score for the NPI block was 31.64 ± 3.4 , which is significantly lower than normal ($p < 0.01$). The study of thinking in this group showed a significant difference from the norm ($p < 0.01$) according to the "Exclusion of excess" method (8.5 ± 0.46), and errors were rare in excluding an unnecessary word, but difficulties arose when choosing the name of a group of words, i.e. a categorical definition. Sometimes patients resorted to using words given in the enumeration of the vocabulary or to specific situational connections, which indicates a decrease in semantic memory. Cognitive decline in dyscirculatory encephalopathy progresses from deterioration of attention, modal-nonspecific forms of memory, pace of thinking at stage I of the disease to a decrease in all types of memory, attention, constructive apraxia, visual agnosia, anosognosia, disorders of planning and regulation of activity at stage III of the disease in vascular dementia. An increase in age has an effect on a decrease in attention, visual and semantic memory. Based on the dominant clinical disorders, variants of cognitive and emotional disorders in dyscirculatory encephalopathy are identified, which are most clearly manifested at stage II: dysmnestic, depressive, paranoid and emotionally labile, which are characterized by neuropsychological and neurological signs. In each of the variants of cognitive and emotional

disorders, individual neurological syndromes are determined with a similar frequency: pyramidal, pseudobulbar, atactic, cochleo-vestibular, dissomnic and cephalgic. The greatest association of focal neurological disorders and psychopathological disorders was found in vascular dementia.

Thus, at the first stage of DE, there is a discrepancy between subjective and objective assessments of cognitive functions, which indicates both the lability of mental functions, flickering symptoms characteristic of cerebral vascular disorders, and the presence of an asthenic symptom complex.

References:

1. DcS, professor Khodjieva D.T., Yuldosheva N.K. "Specificity of cognitive impairment in chronic cerebral ischemia". International scientific and practical Conference: Modern views and research – 2021, July, 2021: Egham, London. Independent Publishing Network Ltd – 52 p. (page 23-24)
2. PhD, associate Professor Akhrorova Sh.B., Yuldosheva N.K. "Features of cognitive and emotional disorders in chronic cerebral ischemia". Journal of Neurology and neurosurgery research volume 2, issue 3 – 2021 (pp. 50-53)
3. Yuldosheva N.K. "Cognitive disorders in patients with chronic brain ischemia" Amaliy va Tibbiyot fanlari ilmiy jurnali "Ekologiya va ekologik ta'lim muammolari" maxsus son – 2022. (323-326 bet)
4. Yuldosheva N.K. "Features and dynamics of disorders of cognitive and static-locomotor functions in chronic brain ischemia". Journal of GALAXY INTERNATIONAL INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL (GIIRJ) ISSN (E): 2347-6915 Vol. 11, Issue 10, Oct. (2023) <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/4466>
5. Yuldosheva N.K. "Морфологический аспекты нарушение мелкий моторики при хронический ишемии головного мозга" Journal of Iqro volume 7, issue 1 - 2023 special issue (pp. 94-99) <https://wordlyknowledge.uz/index.php/iqro/article/view/3245>
6. Yuldosheva N.K. "Morphological aspects of static-locomotor function disorders in chronic cerebral ischemia" Journal of International Journal of Medical Sciences And Clinical Research (ISSN – 2771-2265) VOLUME 03 ISSUE 12 PAGES: 7-12 <http://theusajournals.com/index.php/ijmscr/article/view/2002>

